

6G Monitoring Agents in Autonomous Disaggregated Optical Transport Network

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Abstract—As network technology evolves toward 6G, effective network-monitoring systems become essential to support automation and intelligence. These systems must enable accurate, real-time data collection while maintaining flexibility for diverse data sources. This paper introduces two versatile, data-agnostic telemetry systems designed to address the complexities of next-generation 6G networks. The first system, the *CONTELEM-Monitoring-Agent*, provides real-time, multi-source telemetry with fault detection, performance optimization, and automated network management. Its modular, plugin-based architecture supports dynamic integration of various data sources. The second system, the *WHITOPEN OpenConfig/gNMI Agent*, offers a standardized interface for configuring and managing network elements, enabling real-time monitoring through an OpenConfig and gNMI frameworks. Both systems offer scalable and adaptable performance across various network configurations. The paper details related technologies, modular architectures, and experimental validation using an autonomous SDN controller. Finally, it highlights key contributions and explores future enhancements

Index Terms—6G Network Telemetry, gNMI, Network Telemetry Agent, Packet/optical nodes, Optical SDN Controller, Disaggregated Optical Systems

I. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid evolution of network technology, particularly in the transition to 6G, effective network-monitoring systems have become indispensable for overcoming network automation and intelligence [1] [2]. For these types of networks, tools enabling accurate, real-time operational data collection will be crucial, while remaining flexibility to accommodate diverse data sources. In this paper, we introduce two versatile, data-agnostic telemetry systems developed to meet the expanding demands and complexities of next-generation 6G communication networks. The first one, the *CONTELEM-Monitoring-Agent*, addresses these needs by offering real-time, multi-source telemetry capabilities that enable fault detection, performance optimization, and automated network management. The agent utilizes a plugin-based architecture that

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allows integration of multiple data sources through dynamically registered plugins. The agent’s modular architecture and Northbound Interface functionalities are also detailed in our methodology, covering workflows such as plugin registration, data retrieval, and telemetry subscriptions. The second telemetry system is the *WHITOPEN OpenConfig/gNMI Agent*, that provides an OpenConfig/NETCONF interface for configuring and managing network elements of the involved NOS, that in addition with the SONiC telemetry container, enables real-time network monitoring and streaming of operational data. The design of both Monitoring agents allow to deliver scalable and adaptable performance, supporting efficient telemetry across diverse network configurations. The paper presents the both developed agents, that is a network telemetry solutions for optical transport systems. It first reviews related technologies and protocols (Section II) before detailing the modular, plugin-based architecture for both (Section III). An experimental validation shows the utilization of telemetry agents on a modern autonomous SDN controller system (Section IV). And finally, the paper summarizes contributions and explores future enhancements (Section V).

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

This section provides a brief state-of-the-art analysis of the key components involved in integrating telemetry into packet/optical switching nodes. In addition, the requirements for the telemetry agent to be deployed in the switching nodes will be defined, based on the already published deliverables of the 6G-OPTRAN project. Specifically, we will study (II-A) elements and devices, (II-B) data models and interfaces, (II-C) network management protocols and (II-D) optical SDN controllers.

A. Elements and devices

Within the framework of optical network systems, the telemetry agent must support unbundled optical systems and optical transponder. This subsection highlights all the elements and devices that exist in the state of the art, including their main characteristics. Disaggregated optical systems [3] are modular network architectures that separate optical components, allowing flexible, scalable, and vendor-neutral integration to meet diverse network needs. Several Disaggregated Optical Systems exists, including Cassini, Phoenix, Galileo, and Voyager, which can potentially be integrated as data

sources for the CONTELEM-Monitoring-Agent. As Disaggregated Optical Systems studied, only Cassini (Edgecore AS7716-24SC) is the system that supports an open NOS with a proven track record [4]. Cassini is an open and unbundled 200G transponder and routing platform developed by Edgecore Networks and contributed to the Telecom Infra Project (TIP). It combines packet switching and optical transport functions in a single modular platform, providing flexibility and scalability for network operators. Cassini supports multiple transponder modules, enabling data transmission over different optical interfaces and distances. It also incorporates routing capabilities, enabling aggregation and switching of traffic at the network edge. SONiC [13] is an open-source, Linux-based NOS that has gained significant popularity in intra-DC networks due to its robust networking capabilities. However, it is important to note that SONiC lacks native support for NETCONF and coherent transceivers. The GoldStone Project [7] aims to address these limitations by integrating open-source components from OCP and TIP, such as ONL, SAI, and TAI, to develop a modular NOS for packet-optical nodes. This architecture simplifies the management of ASIC-based Ethernet switches and coherent transceivers while offering the flexibility to support various optical networking devices in the future.

B. Data models and interfaces

Since the architecture of an optical transport network is composed of multiple types of components from various domains (optical and packet) and multiple manufacturers. Standardization bodies as well as manufacturers and operators define different interfaces for the management and abstraction of the components of the optical transport network architecture. An optical transport network architecture [10] is composed of three different types of interfaces (OpenConfig, TIP OOPT - TAI and ONF T-API). On the other hand, there is also Open ROADM, which specifies all the ROADM components as well as the transponders and connectable optical elements. OpenConfig [6] is an open source initiative that focuses on defining and promoting standardized data models for network device management. These data models provide a common and uniform representation of network devices and their configurations, facilitating the automation and management of heterogeneous networks. ONF T-API is a standardized interface (and API) for managing optical transport networks. This API allows network management applications to interact with network devices in a uniform manner, regardless of their manufacturer or specific model. Open ROADM is an unbundled optical network architecture that enables service providers to create open, scalable and flexible networks capable of supporting a wide variety of services and applications.

C. Network management protocols

The data models and interfaces described in the previous section require network management protocols to interact with the components of the transport network architecture. That

is why this subsection explores standard network management protocols such as NETCONF, RESTCONF, or gNMI for metric extraction [9]. NETCONF is used to configure, manipulate and retrieve the configuration of network devices. Main features: configuration and operation of network devices, configuration operations (get-config, edit-config, etc.), support for YANG data models. Its main focus is the configuration and operation of network devices. RESTCONF provides a programmatic interface for configuring and managing network devices using the principles of Representational State Transfer (REST). Its main focus is on device configuration and operation. gNMI is designed to provide a more efficient, scalable and flexible way to manage network devices compared to traditional protocols such as SNMP or NETCONF. It supports telemetry efficiently by offering subscriptions and bidirectional data transmission, allowing customers to receive updates continuously without the need for repeated polling.

In summary [11], gNMI emerges as a superior choice due to its efficiency, scalability, and native support for subscriptions and bidirectional data transmission.

D. Optical SDN Controllers

Software-Defined Networking (SDN) in the latest years introduced a centralized control paradigm that enhances programmability, automation, and scalability. They serve as intelligent orchestrators, enabling seamless interoperability across heterogeneous, multi-vendor environments. These controllers also leverage real-time telemetry data, closed-loop automation to optimize service delivery, and dynamically adapt to evolving network demands.

III. INTEGRATION AND WORKFLOW OF GNMI AGENTS

In this section, the architectures of the telemetry agents, *CONTELEM-Monitoring-Agent* and *WHITOPEN OpenConfig/gNMI Agent* are defined, as well as the corresponding workflows for a subset of its functionalities.

A. Architecture and workflow of CONTELEM-Monitoring-Agent On Cassini

This telemetry agent architecture is designed to be modular and scalable, allowing easy integration with different data sources and facilitating the addition of new functionality. The telemetry agent links the telemetry server to various data sources within the Whitebox and NOS, including Platform APIs, Switching Processors or even transceiver and optical transponder management platforms. The main components of the telemetry agent (see Figure 1) are the Telemetry server, the Telemetry Agent — Core and the Telemetry Agent — Plugin. The telemetry server implements a *gnmi.proto* client to communicate with the telemetry agent and perform telemetry subscriptions. The telemetry agent core is in charge of managing the gNMI subscriptions made from the telemetry server and making the relevant queries to the plugins using the *telemetry.proto*. The Telemetry agent plugins are responsible for registering against the telemetry agent core through the *registry.proto* communications interface. Once registered, the plugins listen to telemetry requests received from the telemetry

Fig. 1. Telemetry agent architecture - NBI, SBI and core

Fig. 2. Data flow for telemetry data subscription

agent core. In the North Bound Interface, the telemetry agent supports all telemetry features defined in gNMI specification [5], namely GET, POLL, and SUBSCRIPTION. Figure 2 shows the data flow to subscribe to telemetry from a data source supported by the telemetry agent, via some plugin.

B. WHITOPEN OpenConfig/gNMI Agent on SONiC

The SONiC operating system (Software for Open Networking in the Cloud) is a software framework that employs a microservices-based architecture, in which networking functions are containerized using Docker. It is Linux-based, with the Switch Abstraction Interface (SAI) providing hardware independence, while Docker-based containers ensure modularity and extensibility. In the context of the development of WhitOpen OpenConfig/gNMI Agent, we would like to highlight some of them directly implicated in it. The Redis database functions as the central data store, managing configurations and real-time network states. It facilitates centralized communication among SONiC components, thereby maintain-

ing consistency across the system. It employs a publisher-subscriber model, enabling containers to dynamically update and respond to state changes in an event-driven manner. The Switch State Services (SWSS) container functions as the central communication element for the pool of SONiC components, thereby serving as a bridge between the high-level configuration of SONiC and the underlying switch hardware. The Platform Monitoring (PMON) container is responsible for the oversight and management of the hardware components that constitute the switch. It gathers and disseminates information from peripherals such as temperature, fans, LEDs, and power suppliers, and it manages other devices such as transceivers via the *xcvrd*. In examining the fundamental components of the WhitOpen Agent (see Figure 3), it is clear that the telemetry service is executed by the SONiC native container, which facilitates gNMI-based telemetry. The telemetry container in SONiC provides a gNMI server that interacts with the system's state and configuration database to expose telemetry data. As previously delineated for the CONTELEM-Monitoring-agent, the establishment of the telemetry workflow is initiated by the gNMI client through the submission of a subscription request to SONiC's telemetry container. Subsequently, the telemetry container retrieves the requested network state data from SONiC's Redis database, which serves as a repository for real-time configurations and operational metrics. The retrieved data is then formatted using SONiC native YANG models and streamed to the client over gRPC, ensuring high-performance monitoring. The extensibility of SONiC has been augmented with the development of a NETCONF Server Agent that operates within a dedicated Docker container. This agent has been built upon Netopeer2 with the logic of the custom agent implemented in Python. It facilitates remote management and configuration of optical pluggable interfaces, which are integrated within the white-box chassis that supports SONiC. Especially, it provides a standardized OpenConfig YANG-based interface for configuring and managing network elements. When a NETCONF client request asks for a change, such as modifying the configuration of an optical pluggable interface, the agent writes the new configuration into ConfigDB within Redis. SONiC's internal mechanisms then detect the update and trigger the appropriate workflow to apply changes to the pluggable hardware.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

As demonstrated in [14], experimental validation has shown the efficacy of an autonomous SDN controller in transforming optical transport networks into intelligent, self-healing systems. The framework unifies open control interfaces with real-time telemetry in a disaggregated multi-vendor environment, thereby enabling the dynamic provisioning of quality-of-transmission (QoT)-assured connectivity services and the execution of proactive recovery strategies. A key component of this framework is the gNMI Agent, which enables communication between heterogeneous network operating systems and streams granular optical performance metrics, including critical transponder parameters such as *OSNR* and *PRE-*

Fig. 3. Architecture of WhiteOpen Agent on a SONiC NOS

FEC-BER, directly to the controller. This continuous flow of physical-layer intelligence enables autonomous decision-making, wherein the controller not only detects service disruptions but also autonomously mitigates subtle QoT degradations before they escalate. In response to real-time network health data, the controller recalibrates lightpaths or triggers protection mechanisms. Following these design principles, Figure 4 illustrates the architecture of an autonomous Optical Software-Defined Networking (SDN) Controller developed to manage a disaggregated optical transport network within the CTTC ADRENALINE testbed[®]. The optical terminals (OTs) adopt a white-box approach powered by the SONiC NOS, which enables the configuration of disaggregated, multi-vendor transponder components, including ASICs and coherent pluggable transceivers. These 400G QSFP-DD ZR+ transceivers support the configuration of C-band central frequency, output Tx power, and various operational modes based on different symbol rates (30 and 60 Gbaud) and modulation formats (DP-QPSK, DP-8QAM, and DP-16QAM). Additionally, the SDN controller incorporates a robust telemetry system to support closed-loop operations, ensuring service quality and enabling proactive recovery strategies for both hard and soft network failures. Two recovery strategies are considered: re-routing (with a break-before-make approach) and updating approaches.

Once the service has been configured, the SDN controller receives monitoring and telemetry data from the OTs. The controller subscribes to either a periodic or event-driven basis to receive the data. The telemetry data, transmitted through gNMI, includes metrics such as received OSNR and *PRE-FEC-BER* levels. These metrics allow the SDN controller to assess any degradation in the connection’s Quality of Transmission (QoT). Network anomalies, such as high-power interference or C-band noise, degrade QoT, prompting a gNMI notification with updated *PRE-FEC-BER* values. To restore service, the SDN controller either re-routes traffic through an

Fig. 4. Autonomous Optical SDN Controller in CTTC ADRENALINE testbed

alternative path while maintaining the initial SLA terms of the service or notifies the user of the issue and suggests a solution.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper presented two monitoring agents as robust telemetry solution, validated for accurate real-time monitoring in multi-vendor network environments. The experimental validation on CTTC’s ADRENALINE Testbed[®] highlights the agent’s interoperability and adaptability, showcasing it as a reliable tool for advanced network management and monitoring.

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